

Study of uncatalyzed and Ir^{III} catalyzed oxidation of D-(+)dextrose by ceric ammonium sulphate – A kinetic study in acidic medium

Sonal Choubey^{a,b*}, Surendra K. Rajput^a and Kishor N. Bapat^a

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Govt. Nagarjun P.G. College, Raipur-492 010, Chhattisgarh, India

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Disha Institute of Management and Technology, Raipur-492 010, Chhattisgarh, India

E-mail : sonalchoube@gmail.com

Manuscript received 29 April 2010, revised 17 October 2011, accepted 09 November 2011

Abstract : The kinetics of uncatalysed and catalysed oxidation of D-(+)dextrose by cerium(IV) has been studied in acidic medium in the temperature range 303–338 K. The reaction has been found to be first order with respect to [D-(+)dextrose] in both uncatalysed and catalysed reactions. The rates follow first order kinetics in [Ir^{III}] catalysed oxidation reaction. The effect of [HSO₄⁻] has also been observed. The increase in ionic strength of the medium decreases the rate of uncatalysed reaction while increases catalysed reaction. The 1 : 2 stoichiometry is observed in the oxidation. From the effect of temperature on the reaction rate, the Arrhenius and activation parameters have been calculated. A suitable mechanism has been proposed and a rate law explaining the experimental results is derived.

Keywords : D-(+)Dextrose, cerium(IV), kinetics, Ir^{III}, catalysis.

Introduction

The study of carbohydrates is one of the most exciting fields of organic chemistry. Carbohydrates serve as the chief fuel of biological systems, in living organism. They are the primary source of energy in plants, animals and human beings. Energy is stored in the complex molecular structure of the carbohydrates. The atoms arrange themselves back into simple compounds during the metabolism of complex compounds, and, in the process, release their stored energy for our use. Carbohydrates must be burned or oxidized if energy is to be released.

A vast amount of literature is available on the kinetics of oxidation of carbohydrates by various organic and inorganic oxidants. The oxidation of aldoses by chlorine and bromine have been reported in alkaline media^{1,2}. The use of periodate in the uncatalyzed oxidation of carbohydrates and Ru^{III} and the ruthenate ion-catalyzed oxidation of reducing sugars in an alkaline medium are available³. From the previous work on cerium oxidation it has been seen that cerium is a strong oxidizing agent and it can oxidize various organic and inorganic substances such as amino acids⁴, antimony(III)⁵, 4-piperidones⁶, formic

acid⁷, phenethyl alcohols⁸, glycols⁹, dialkylsulphoxides¹⁰, tellurium(IV)¹¹, toluene, benzene (Ru catalyzed)¹², cyclic alcohol¹³ and cyclic ketones (Ru catalyzed)¹⁴ etc.

In the present paper, the primary aim is to ascertain the catalysed and uncatalyzed molecular reaction of D-(+)dextrose by the titrimetric method in view of the biological importance of this reducing sugar. The mechanism and kinetics of oxidation of reducing sugar is very important tool in medicinal and organic chemistry therefore it is beneficial to explore the kinetics of oxidation of sugars by cerium(IV).

Results and discussion

Under the condition [S] >> [Ce^{IV}] >> [Ir^{III}], the reaction is studied at different concentration of D-(+)dextrose at fixed concentrations of other reactants. The order of reaction with respect to substrate D-(+)dextrose is determined at fixed concentration of cerium(IV) for different concentrations of D-(+)dextrose. The results are given in Tables 1 and 2.

The result shows that the rate constant is directly pro-

Table 1. Effect of variation of [D-(+)dextrose]; on the reaction rate

$10^3 [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] = 4.0 \text{ M}; 10 [\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 5.0 \text{ M}; \text{Temp.} = 303 \text{ K}$

Run no.	10 [D-(+)dextrose] (M)	$k_1 \times 10^4$ (min ⁻¹)
1	1	7.2
2	2	9.8
3	3	11.9
4	4	13.4
5	5	14.7

Table 2. Effect of variation of [D-(+)dextrose]; on the reaction rate

$10^3 [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] = 4.0 \text{ M}; 10 [\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 5.0 \text{ M}; 10^6 [\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}] = 2.4 \text{ M}; \text{Temp.} = 303 \text{ K}$

Run no.	10 [D-(+)dextrose] (M)	$k_2 \times 10^3$ (min ⁻¹)
1	1	5.70
2	2	8.77
3	4	12.9
4	5	16.2
5	8	17.5
6	10	19.2
7	12	22.5

portional to the concentration of D-(+)dextrose for both uncatalysed and catalysed system. The plot of $1/k_1$ vs $1/[\text{D-(+)dextrose}]$ and plot of $\log k_1$ vs $\log [\text{D-(+)dextrose}]$ are linear.

In order to see the effect of $[\text{H}^+]$ ion concentration on the reaction rate, it has been found that the reaction rate decreases with increase of sulphuric acid concentration in uncatalysed oxidation while increases in Ir^{III} catalysed oxidation. The reaction has been carried out at various initial concentration of H_2SO_4 acid. $[\text{H}^+]$ is varied over the range 0.5–2.0 M while other reactants are constant. The results are given in Tables 3 and 4. Because of the involvement of large number of proton dependent equilibria in the cerium(IV), the exact computation on $[\text{H}^+]$ is not possible. The inhibition of reaction rate by the addition of H_2SO_4 may be due to the removal of reactive species of cerium(IV). The results indicate the involvement of cerium(IV)-sulphato species.

The above data indicates that the rate is dependent on the catalyst concentration. When a graph is plotted between IrCl_3 concentration and the rate constant, a linear

Table 3. Effect of variation of $[\text{H}^+]$; on the reaction rate

$10^3 [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] = 4.0 \text{ M}; 10 [\text{D-(+)dextrose}] = 5.0 \text{ M}; \text{Temp.} = 303 \text{ K}$

Run no.	10 $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$ (M)	$10^4 k_1$ (min ⁻¹)
1	0.50	14.68
2	0.70	12.50
3	0.90	11.06
4	1.10	10.05
5	1.20	9.43
6	1.30	6.70
7	1.50	7.90

Table 4. Effect of variation of $[\text{H}^+]$; on the reaction rate

$10^3 [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] = 4.0 \text{ M}; 10^6 [\text{IrCl}_3] = 2.4 \text{ M}; 10 [\text{D-(+)dextrose}] = 5.0 \text{ M}; \text{Temp.} = 303 \text{ K}$

Run no.	10 $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$ (M)	$10^3 k_1$ (min ⁻¹)
1	5.00	16.20
2	7.0	19.5
3	11.0	22.2
4	13.0	24.5
5	17.0	26.8
6	21.0	32.7

curve is obtained indicating that the rate is linearly related to IrCl_3 concentration. The results so obtained are represented in Table 5. The reaction rate increases with increase in $[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]$ and the plot of $\log k_1$ vs $\log [\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]$ is linear.

Table 5. Effect of variation of [Catalyst]; on the reaction rate

$10^3 [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] = 4.0 \text{ M}; 10 [\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 5.0 \text{ M}; 10 [\text{D-(+)dextrose}] = 5.0 \text{ M}; \text{Temp.} = 303 \text{ K}$

Run no.	$10^6 \times [\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]$ (M)	$10^3 \times k_1$ (min ⁻¹)
1	2.40	16.20
2	4.00	18.40
3	6.00	20.76
4	8.00	22.41
5	10.00	25.30
6	12.00	27.35

The reactions are studied in the range of $0.4\text{--}5.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$ of potassium hydrogen sulphate, while keeping all other reactants constant $[\text{H}^+]$ ($[\text{H}^+] = 0.5 \text{ M}$), $[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]$, $[\text{S}]$, $[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]$, μ and T . Here $[\text{HSO}_4^-] \approx [\text{KHSO}_4] + [\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$ ignoring the dissociation of $[\text{HSO}_4^-]$ in the strongly acidic

solution. The observations are given in Table 6. The graphical plot for the $\log k_1$ vs $\log [\text{HSO}_4^-]$ is found to be a straight line, which indicates that the rate of the reaction is inversely proportional to the $[\text{HSO}_4^-]$ ion concentration. As the concentration of this electrolyte increases, the concentration of cerium(IV) at the reaction site decreases due to salting-out effect of the salts. Thus, exclusion effect seems to be responsible for rate decrease in presence of inorganic electrolytes. Thus the hydrogen sulfate dependence can be represented as eq. (1).

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{a}{b + c [\text{HSO}_4^-]} \quad (1)$$

where a , b and c are constants under the experimental conditions.

$[\text{H}^+]$ is varied over the range 0.5–2.0 M at fixed $[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]$, $[\text{S}]$ and $[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]$. $[\text{H}^+]$ is calculated ignoring the

dissociation of $[\text{HSO}_4^-]$ and assuming $[\text{H}^+] \approx [\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$. Here k_{obs} increase obviously with the increase of $[\text{H}^+]$. The plot of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ against $1/[\text{H}^+]$ at 298 K is found to be linear with a positive intercept and slope. The results are given in Table 4.

Mechanism of the reaction : The kinetic data (i.e. $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $1/[\text{S}]$) fits well with the Michaelis-Menten model, suggesting that 1 : 1 type complex of substrate and Ir^{III} is formed in the first equilibrium step.

Substrate is easily protonised in acid media, indicating involvement of H^+ in the reaction in the pre equilibrium step. $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2$ has been found kinetically active in this study with generation of free radicals in the reaction. Thus a mechanism consistent with the above kinetics is proposed (Scheme 1).

where '2' indicates that 1 mole of substrate is oxidized by 2 moles of Ce^{IV} . The above eq. (1) can also be written as shown in eq. (2) from the mechanism below

Scheme 1. Mechanism of oxidation of D-(+)dextrose in presence of Ir^{III} catalyst.

In eq. (6), Ce^{IV*} represents any species of Ce^{IV} . Step (5) is the rate determining step. According to the present mechanism, applying the steady-state condition to the free radicals¹⁶.

$$k_{obs} = \frac{2fk_s k_1 k_3 [Ir^{III}]_T [S] [H^+]}{k_3 [S] [H^+] + k_2} \quad (7)$$

Here, f denotes the fraction of kinetically active species to the total cerium(IV) and subscript T stands for total concentration. Based on the above mechanism, the rate law can be established as follows :

$$\frac{-d[Complex]_1}{dt} = k_1 [Ir^{III}]_T [Ce^{IV}] - k_2 [Complex]_1 - k_3 [Complex]_1 [S] [H^+] \quad (8)$$

Applying steady state hypothesis

$$-d[Complex]_1/dt = 0$$

Hence $k_1 [Ir^{III}]_T [Ce^{IV}] =$

$$k_2 [Complex]_1 + k_3 [Complex]_1 [S] [H^+] \quad (9)$$

Therefore, the concentration of the complex becomes

$$[Complex]_1 = \frac{k_1 [Ir^{III}]_T [Ce^{IV}]}{\{k_2 + k_3 [S] [H^+]\}} \quad (10)$$

At steady state condition, the rate of disappearance of $[Ce^{IV}]$ as given as eq. (2).

$$\frac{-d[Ce^{IV}]}{dt} = 2k_s [Complex]_2 \quad (2)$$

or

$$\frac{-d[Ce^{IV}]}{dt} = 2k_s k_3 [S] [H^+] [Complex]_1 \quad (11)$$

Putting the value of $[Complex]_1$

$$\frac{-d[Ce^{IV}]}{dt} = \frac{2k_s k_1 k_3 [S] [H^+] [Ir^{III}]_T [Ce^{IV}]}{\{k_2 + k_3 [S] [H^+]\}} \quad (12)$$

Now, the total $[Ce^{IV}]$ may be considered as :

$$[Ce^{IV}]_T = [Ce^{IV}]_e + [Complex]_1 \quad (13)$$

Putting the value of $[Complex]_1$

$$[Ce^{IV}]_T = \frac{[Ce^{IV}]_e + k_1 [Ir^{III}]_T [Ce^{IV}]}{\{k_2 + k_3 [S] [H^+]\}} \quad (14)$$

$$[Ce^{IV}]_T = \frac{[Ce^{IV}]_e \{k_2 + k_3 [S] [H^+]\} + [k_1 [Ir^{III}]_T [Ce^{IV}]}{\{k_2 + k_3 [S] [H^+]\}} \quad (15)$$

The value of $[Ce^{IV}]_T$ comes out to be :

$$[Ce^{IV}]_T = \frac{[Ce^{IV}]_T \{k_2 + k_3 [S] [H^+]\}}{\{k_2 + k_3 [S] [H^+]\} + \{k_1 [Ir^{III}]_T\}} \quad (16)$$

From eqs. (7) and (11), the final rate law comes out to be :

$$\frac{-d[Ce^{IV}]}{dt} = \frac{2k_s k_1 k_3 [S] [H^+] [Ir^{III}]_T}{\{k_2 + k_3 [S] [H^+]\}} \times \frac{[Ce^{IV}]_T \{k_2 + k_3 [S] [H^+]\}}{\{k_2 + k_3 [S] [H^+]\} + \{k_1 [Ir^{III}]_T\}} \quad (17)$$

$$\frac{-d[Ce^{IV}]}{dt} = \frac{2k_s k_1 k_3 [S] [H^+] [Ir^{III}]_T [Ce^{IV}]_T}{\{k_2 + k_3 [S] [H^+]\} + \{k_1 [Ir^{III}]_T\}} \quad (18)$$

Under the present experimental condition, one might assume the following inequality :

$$\{k_2 + k_3 [S] [H^+]\} \gg \{k_1 [Ir^{III}]_T\} \quad (19)$$

And hence. eq. (11) reduces to :

$$\frac{-d[Ce^{IV}]}{dt} = \frac{2k_s k_1 k_3 [S] [H^+] [Ir^{III}]_T [Ce^{IV}]_T}{k_2 + k_3 [S] [H^+]} \quad (20)$$

$$k_{obs} = \frac{\frac{-d[Ce^{IV}]}{dt}}{[Ce^{IV}]_T} = \frac{2k_s k_1 k_3 [S] [H^+] [Ir^{III}]_T}{k_2 + k_3 [S] [H^+]} \quad (21)$$

$$\frac{1}{k_{obs}} = \frac{1}{2k_s k_1 [Ir^{III}]_T} + \frac{1}{2k_s k_1 k_3 [S] [H^+] [Ir^{III}]_T} \quad (22)$$

From the plot $1/k_{obs}$ against $1/[S]$ is made from which the constants $1/k_s k_1$ and $k_2/k_s k_1 k_3$ are determined from the slope and intercept respectively. According to the equation above; when plots are made between $1/k_{obs}$ and $1/[S]$, a positive intercept would be observed which confirms the validity of the mechanism and also the rate law. Eq. (22) also suggests that the plot of $1/k_{obs}$ versus $1/[H^+]$ at constant $[Ir^{III}]_T$ and $[S]$ should also be linear. $1/k_{obs}$ versus $1/[Ir^{III}]$ at constant $[S]$ and $[H^+]$ should yield good linear plots through the origin.

The values of $k_s k_1 k_3$ and k_2 for $[S]$ can also be calculated from the double reciprocal plots.

Since Ir^{III} is inert¹⁷ in the proposed mechanism, it may bond to [Ce⁴⁺] to form an outer-sphere complex (Ir⁴⁺.....Ce³⁺), which is rapidly reduced into an inner-sphere complex by D-(+)dextrose. As Ir⁴⁺ is unstable, the free radicals can be generated through an inner-sphere electron transfer process between Ir⁴⁺ and D-(+)dextrose. Meanwhile, Ir³⁺ and the partially oxidized product can be obtained. Thus, the oxidation of D-(+)dextrose occurs through the Ir³⁺/Ir⁴⁺ catalytic cycle.

Kinetically active Ce^{IV} species :

Under the experimental conditions in aqueous sulfuric acid medium, the important cerium(IV) sulfato complexes are Ce(SO₄)²⁺, Ce(SO₄)₂ and HCe(SO₄)₃⁻ and the relevant equilibrium are¹⁵

Among the different sulfato species, the kinetically active species should be inferred on the basis of kinetic data, not according to the magnitude of concentration¹⁸.

From the relationship between hydrogen sulphate and *k*_{obs} Ce(SO₄)₂ has been found as the kinetically active species in the present study. The concentration of Ce(SO₄)₂ can be approximately obtained. According to the mass balance eq. (26) is obtained.

$$[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]_{\text{T}} = [\text{Ce}^{4+}] + [\text{Ce(SO}_4\text{)}^{2+}] + [\text{Ce(SO}_4\text{)}_2] + [\text{HCe(SO}_4\text{)}_3^-] \quad (26)$$

From eqs. (23–25), the following equations can be derived

$$[\text{Ce}^{4+}] = \frac{[\text{Ce(SO}_4\text{)}_2][\text{H}^+]^2}{B_1 B_2 [\text{HSO}_4^-]^2}$$

$$[\text{Ce(SO}_4\text{)}^{2+}] = \frac{[\text{Ce(SO}_4\text{)}_2][\text{H}^+]}{B_2 [\text{HSO}_4^-]}$$

$$[\text{Ce(SO}_4\text{)}_2] = \frac{[\text{HCe(SO}_4\text{)}_3^-]}{[\text{HSO}_4^-] B_3}$$

$$[\text{HCe(SO}_4\text{)}_3^-] = B_3 [\text{Ce(SO}_4\text{)}_2] [\text{HSO}_4^-]$$

Substituting the above equation into eq. (1) we get

$$[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]_{\text{T}} = \frac{[\text{Ce(SO}_4\text{)}_2][\text{H}^+]^2}{B_1 B_2 [\text{HSO}_4^-]^2} + \frac{[\text{H}^+][\text{Ce(SO}_4\text{)}_2]}{B_2 [\text{HSO}_4^-]} + [\text{Ce(SO}_4\text{)}_2] + B_3 [\text{Ce(SO}_4\text{)}_2] [\text{HSO}_4^-] \quad (27)$$

By considering the relative magnitudes of successive formation equilibrium constants which are in the order *B*₁ >> *B*₂ >> *B*₃ the value of $\frac{[\text{Ce(SO}_4\text{)}_2][\text{H}^+]^2}{B_1 B_2 [\text{HSO}_4^-]^2}$ and $\frac{[\text{H}^+][\text{Ce(SO}_4\text{)}_2]}{B_2 [\text{HSO}_4^-]}$ are much less than the latter two terms.

Therefore, we get eq. (3) from eq. (2).

$$[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]_{\text{T}} \approx [\text{Ce(SO}_4\text{)}_2] + B_3 [\text{Ce(SO}_4\text{)}_2] [\text{HSO}_4^-] \quad (28)$$

$$\text{So, } [\text{Ce(SO}_4\text{)}_2] = \frac{[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]_{\text{T}}}{1 + B_3 [\text{HSO}_4^-]} = f [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]_{\text{T}}$$

$$f = \frac{1}{1 + B_3 [\text{HSO}_4^-]} \quad (29)$$

Substituting eq. (29) into eq. (7), we get

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{2k_3 k_1 k_3 [\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}} [\text{S}] [\text{H}^+]}{(k_3 [\text{S}] [\text{H}^+] + k_2) (1 + B_3 [\text{HSO}_4^-])} \quad (30)$$

$$\text{Assuming } m = \frac{2k_3 k_1 k_3 [\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}} [\text{S}] [\text{H}^+]}{k_3 [\text{S}] [\text{H}^+] + k_2}$$

Eq. (30) may be written as

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{m}{1 + B_3 [\text{HSO}_4^-]} \quad (31)$$

$$\frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{1}{m} + \frac{B_3}{m} [\text{HSO}_4^-] \quad (32)$$

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{a}{b + c [\text{HSO}_4^-]} \quad (1)$$

Eq. (31) is the same as eq. (1) which can explain well the negative number order dependence on [HSO₄⁻], eq. (32) suggests that 1/*k*_{obs} versus [HSO₄⁻] should be linear and agrees with the observed experimental data. From the slope (*B*₃/*m*) and intercept (1/*m*) obtained by the linear regression of 1/*k*_{obs} versus [HSO₄⁻]_n the ratio of slope to intercept is calculated i.e. *B*₃ is estimated to be same according to eq. (32), which is in good agreement with previously reported value^{15,19}. All the above results show that Ce(SO₄)₂ is the kinetically active species. Furthermore, the ionic strength has little effect on *k*_{obs}. Accord-

ing to the principle of salt effect, there must be a neutral molecule in rate determining step, which confirms $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2$ as the kinetically active species in the present study.

In considering the result of kinetic studies the complex forming ability of the acid anion with cerium(IV) must be considered. Thus, cerium(IV) oxidations in sulphuric acid, where the sulphate anion forms a stable complex with cerium(IV).

However, recent studies of cerium(IV) oxidation of aldose²⁰ and oxalate²¹ in sulphuric acid report evidence for complex formation. It appears that detection of cerium(IV)-sugar complexes is dependent on the stability of the cerium(IV) inorganic species present. Increasing the stability of the cerium(IV) acid anion complex decreases the probability of detecting cerium(IV) sugar complexes. It can be detected whether the effect of increasing cerium(IV) acid anion complex stability actually affects a change in mechanism with a change in acid. The kinetics of this reaction are studied and showed that D-(+)dextrose²² and cerium(IV) interact in an equilibrium step to form an intermediate complex which is assumed to disproportionate forming a free radical and reduced cerium(III).

The kinetics of this reaction are studied and showed that D-(+)dextrose²³, cerium(IV) and Ir^{III} interact in two equilibrium steps to form an intermediate complex which is assumed to disproportionate forming a free radical and reduced to cerium(III). It is believed to involve both C_1 and C_2 hydroxyls in a complex. In Scheme 1, the reaction mechanism described above is depicted, which explains the products and kinetics of D-dextrose²²⁻²⁴ oxidation by cerium^{IV}.

Such mechanism²⁵ is possible, involving the free aldehydic form of the reducing sugar. In Scheme 1, the mechanism is depicted in two ways since it is not known whether the location of the free radical is determined by factors affecting radical stability or whether the position of the radical is simply the result of chance.

Since the rate of reactions catalysed by iridium ions are very much dependent on the reductant concentrations, it has been suggested²⁶ that these reactions have a common step.

Then in rate determining step Ir^{4+} formed reacts with D-(+)dextrose in presence of H^+ .

The presence of formic acid in the reaction mixture after completion of the reaction has been confirmed by the spot test method²⁷.

Where $[\text{Ir}]_{\text{T}}$ gives the total Ir^{III} concentration. The proposed mechanism involves the formation of Ir^{III} -cerium(IV) complex in a reversible manner which reach with the substrate at the rate determining step to form $[\text{Ir}^{\text{IV}}\text{-cerium(III)-D-(+)dextrose-H}^+]$ complex followed by a slow redox decomposition giving rise to the catalyst and aldoxide radical which is oxidized by cerium(IV)* rapidly. The mechanism is consistent with the existence of the complexes ($\text{Ir}^{\text{IV}}\text{-Ce}^{3+}$) and ($\text{Ir}^{4+}\text{-Ce}^{3+}\text{-D-(+)dextrose-H}^+$).

Oxidation of the sugars at different temperatures from 303 to 338 K is studied. The plots of $\log k_1$ against $1/T$ are linear for both the catalyzed and uncatalyzed oxidation. The Arrhenius activation energy E_a for the uncatalyzed oxidation of D-(+)dextrose is $60.29 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ while the catalyzed oxidation Arrhenius activation energy is $47.76 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$. The value of the uncatalyzed E_a is greater than the E_a of the catalyzed reaction, which suggests that catalysis takes place. The negative entropy of activation ΔS^\ddagger for the catalyzed reaction indicates that the reaction proceed through hybrid transfer between the sugar molecules and Ce^{IV} in presence of Ir^{III} ^{28,29}. This trend is also a characteristic of oxidation of alcohols and

Table 6. Effect of variation of $[\text{KHSO}_4]$ on the reaction rate
 $10^3 [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] = 4.0 \text{ M}$; $10 [\text{D-(+)dextrose}] = 5.0 \text{ M}$; $10 [\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 5.0 \text{ M}$; Temp. = 303 K

Run no.	$10^2 [\text{KHSO}_4] (\text{M})$	$k_1 \times 10^4 (\text{min}^{-1})$
1	0.00	14.68
2	0.50	13.56
3	1.00	11.62
4	2.00	10.72
5	3.00	7.27
6	4.00	5.05
7	5.00	3.29

aldehydes in Ce^{IV}, which is also supported by Mohammed Ilyas *et al.*³³ gives the Arrhenius plot for the catalyzed oxidation of the sugar. Interestingly enough, the value of k_1 for the reaction with D-(+)dextrose 16.2 min^{-1} closely resembles that expected from the combined, parallel reactions of Ce^{IV} with the four alcoholic groups (1 primary and 3 secondary) present in the reductant molecule³⁰.

The molecule of D-(+)dextrose participates in the reaction in its cyclic form rather than in its free aldehyde, linear form. This is consistent with the findings reported for the degradative oxidation of monosaccharides by Ce⁴⁺^{31,32}.

The kinetic data shows the increasing rate of reaction on increasing temperature in both catalyzed and uncatalysed oxidation. The results obtained by study of temperature variation are utilized to calculate various kinetic and activation parameters. The plot of $\log k_1$ vs $1/T$ is linear. The reaction velocities are measured at six different temperatures. All the six experiments are performed at the identical concentration of the reactants. The values of temperature coefficient calculated are given in Tables 7 and 8.

Table 7. Effect of variation of temperature; on the reaction rate
 $10^3 [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] = 4.0 \text{ M}$; $10 [\text{D}(+)\text{dextrose}] = 5.0 \text{ M}$; $10 [\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 5.0 \text{ M}$

Temp. (K)	$1/T \times 10^3$	$k_1 \times 10^4$ (min ⁻¹)
303	3.30	14.69
318	3.14	28.13
323	3.09	34.65
328	3.05	42.63
333	3.00	55.48
338	2.95	67.03

Activation parameters for acidic Ce^{IV} oxidation of D-(+)dextrose

Parameter	D-(+)dextrose
E_a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	60.29
ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	57.60
ΔS^\ddagger (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-29.39
ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	13.54
$\ln A$	17.41

Energy and entropy of activation : The average value of energy of activation (E_a) is found to be 60.29 kJ/mol and 47.76 kJ/mol in uncatalysed and Ir^{III} catalysed oxidation. The value of frequency factor at 323 K is 17.4 min^{-1} and 14.84 min^{-1} entropy of activation at 323 K is -29.39

Table 8. Effect of variation of temperature; on the reaction rate
 $10^3 [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] = 4.0 \text{ M}$; $10 [\text{D}(+)\text{dextrose}] = 5.0 \text{ M}$; $10^6 [\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}] = 2.4$; $10 [\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 5.0 \text{ M}$

Temp. (K)	$1/T \times 10^3$	$k_1 \times 10^3$ (min ⁻¹)
303	3.30	16.0
308	3.25	22.5
313	3.20	28.88
318	3.15	38.22
323	3.10	52.41
333	3.00	85.87

Activation parameters for acidic Ce^{IV} oxidation of D-(+)dextrose

Parameter	D-(+)dextrose
E_a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	47.76
ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	45.07
ΔS^\ddagger (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-29.41
ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	7.9
$\ln A$	14.8

$\text{JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$, $-29.41 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ and free energy of activation (ΔG^\ddagger) $13.54 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, 7.92 kJ mol^{-1} .

The entropy of activation is found to be negative in both cases. The fairly high value of negative ΔS^\ddagger suggests the formation of more ordered activated complex, whereas, the high positive value of the free energy of the activation (ΔG^\ddagger) and enthalpy of activation (ΔH^\ddagger) indicate that the transition state is highly solvated. Formic acid and a aldonic acid with one carbon atom less, are identified in the oxidation of D-(+)dextrose by cerium ammonium sulphate(IV). Energy of activation, free energy of activation and entropy parameters suggest that Ir^{III} forms the activated complex more easily compared to the others. Mechanism consistent with observed rate laws have been suggested.

Experimental

The progress of the reaction between Ce^{IV} and D-(+)dextrose (Merck) in aqueous sulfuric acid medium is studied in the following manner :

Ceric ammonium sulphate (AnalaR) (0.5 M) acidified with sulfuric acid (AR grade) in presence of IrCl₃ (AR) (catalyst), KHSO₄ (salt) and sodiumthiosulfate (AR grade) (reductant) solution of same concentration, taken separately in 250 ml iodine flasks and placed in a thermostat for an hour to attain the temperature of the bath. Ceric ammonium sulfate is stable in acidic solution and do not

show photochemical decomposition or undergo dimerisation. Hence, the rates could be measured in daylight³⁶. Afterwards, the requisite volume of the carbohydrate solution (2–8% of reaction mixture) is sucked out with the help of a pipette and poured into a reaction flask. A stop watch is started when approximately half of carbohydrate solution drained out of the pipette into the reaction vessel^{32–34}. An aliquot of 10 ml of reaction mixture is withdrawn quickly at known intervals of time and poured into another iodine flask containing a drop of 0.05 M potassium iodide (Merck) solution to arrest the reaction. Hypo solution of known concentration is then titrated back against ceric ammonium sulphate solution of the same strength. A micro burette is used for this purpose. From the titre value, the amount of ceric ammonium sulphate present in the aliquot could be easily determined.

Product identification : Completion of the reaction is marked by the complete fading of the yellow color due to Ce^{IV}. One of the reaction products is detected by spot test as Ce^{IV}. The product of oxidation of D-(+)dextrose is detected and estimated by the following method.

The generation of free radicals during the course of the oxidation is confirmed by using acrylonitrile monomer^{35,36}. To a reaction mixture (containing [Ce^{IV}] = 4.0×10^{-3} M, [D-(+)dextrose] = 5.0×10^{-3} and [H₂SO₄] = 0.5 M), (20%, v/v) acrylonitrile is added. Formation of a polymer (white precipitate) appeared slowly, indicating that the reaction system can initiate polymerization of acrylonitrile and also prove the generation of radicals in the reaction³⁷.

Qualitative analysis of the oxidized reaction mixture with the excess [carbohydrate] over [Ce^{IV}] (the kinetic condition) in presence of H₂SO₄ is performed. After the kinetic experiment is completed, a part of the oxidized reaction mixture is treated with alkaline hydroxylamine solution, and the presence of lactones in the reaction mixture is tested by FeCl₃.HCl blue test^{38,39}.

To the other part of the reaction mixture, barium carbonate is added to make the solution neutral³⁹. FeCl₃ solution that has been colored violet with phenol when added to this reaction mixture gave a bright yellow coloration²⁰, indicating the presence of aldonic acid. It is concluded that lactone, formed in the rate determining

step, is hydrolyzed to aldonic acid in neutral medium in a fast step. Formic acid and corresponding acid are confirmed by the help of spot tests²⁷, chemical equivalence and kinetic studies. The identification of aldonic acid are made by comparative paper chromatography and by properties of its diethyldithioacetal derivative.

Qualitative identification of reaction products from cerium(IV) oxidations of various reductants are made by comparative descending paper chromatography. These chromatograms are run on Whatman No. 1 paper exclusively.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Department of Chemistry, Govt. Nagarjuna P.G. College of Science, Raipur and Disha Institute of Engineering and Technology, Raipur for providing apparatus and other facilities.

References

1. N. Bhattacharya and M. L. S. Gupta, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1967, **5**, 554.
2. E. A. Shilov and A. A. Yasnikov, *Khim. Ukr. Zh.*, 1952, 595.
3. K. Singh, N. Chaurasia, S. Rehmani, J. Srivastava and B. Singh, *J. Chem. Res.*, 2005, 304.
4. R. P. Rastogi and P. Chand, *Ind. J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2003, **42**, 1027.
5. (a) V. Devra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **82**, 290; (b) D. C. Bilehal, R. M. Kulkarni and S. T. Nandibewoor, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2003, **83**, 91.
6. D. S. Munawalli, K. A. Thabaj, S. A. Chimatadar and S. T. Nandibewoor, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 2007, **32**, 902.
7. D. S. Munawalli, K. A. Thabaj, S. A. Chimatadar and S. T. Nandibewoor, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 2007, **32**, 902.
8. A. K. Das and M. Das, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1995, **34**, 866.
9. V. B. Rao and M. A. Rao, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2005, **44**, 80.
10. B. Singh, M. Singh and D. Kessarwani, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2002, **41**, 547.
11. S. S. Mohanty, K. K. Sahu and D. Bhatta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1996, **73**, 351.
12. L. S. Dikshitulu, V. H. Rao and S. N. Dindi, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1981, **20**, 784.
13. Praveen K. Tandon, Manish Srivastava, Santosh Kumar and Satpal Singh, *J. Mol. Catal. A : Chem.*, 2009, **304**, 101.
14. Praveen K. Tandon, Alok K. Singh, Sunita Sahgal and

- Santosh Kumar, *J. Mol. Catal. A : Chem.*, 2008, **282**, 136.
15. S. K. Mishra and Y. K. Gupta, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1970, 2918.
 16. A. Z. Wang and T. S. Shi, *Acta Chim. Sin.*, 1988, **46**, 207.
 17. R. G. Wilkins, "The Study of Kinetics and Mechanism of Reaction of Transition Metal Complexes", Allyn and Bacon, Boston, 1974, p. 518.
 18. W. Y. Song, H. Liz and A. Z. Wang, *Chem. J. Chinese Univ.*, 1997, **18**, 1842.
 19. S. K. Mondal, D. Kar, M. Das and A. K. Das, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1998, **37**, 765.
 20. R. N. Mehrotra, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1965, **230**, 221.
 21. Y. A. El-Tantawy and G. A. Rechnitz, *Anal. Chem.*, 1964, **36**, 1774.
 22. "Advances in Carbohydrate Chemistry and Biochemistry", Vol. 60, Derek Horton, 2006.
 23. Sci. Topics Research summaries by experts oxidation bonding electronics, Dr. Sun Chang Qing, 27 June, 2008.
 24. "Advances in Carbohydrate Chemistry and Biochemistry", Vol. 60, Derek Horton, 2006.
 25. B. Krishna and B. P. Sinha, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1959, **212**, 149.
 26. D. A. House, *Chem. Rev.*, 1962, **62**, 185.
 27. Feigl, "Spot Test in Organic Analysis", Elsevier Publishing Company, New York, 1956, p. 208.
 28. K. S. Ashok, N. Chaurasia, R. Shahla, S. Jaya and S. Bharat, *J. Mol. Catal.*, 2004, **95**, 135.
 29. J. Muzart, *Tetrahedron*, 2003, **59**, 5781.
 30. M. A. Maqsood, Z. A. Syed Misbah and K. Zaheer, *Research Letters in Physical Chemistry*, 2007, Article ID 82901.
 31. Joaquin F. Perez-Benito, Conchita Arias, Rosa M. Rodriguez and Marta Ros, *New. J. Chem.*, 1998, 1445.
 32. L. F. Sala, M. A. Rizzotto, S. R. Signoerella, M. I. Frascaroli and S. Acebal, *Oxid. Commun.*, 1991, **14**, 56.
 33. (a) S. S. Muhammad and K. V. Rao, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1963, **36**, 949; (b) I. Vogel, Longman-Green, London, 1958, p. 73.
 34. S. Signorella, M. Rizzotto, V. Dair, M. I. Frascaroli, C. Palopoli, D. Martino, A. Bousseksou and L. F. Sala, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1996, 1607.
 35. A. K. Singh, J. Srivastava and S. Rahmani, *J. Mol. Catal. A : Chem.*, 2007, **271**, 151.
 36. Kabir-ud-din, Ali Mohd, Sajid and Zaheer Khan, *Acta Phys. Chim. Sin.*, 2008, **24**, 810.
 37. (a) K. K. Sengupta, B. A. Begum and B. B. Pal, *Carbohydr. Res.*, 1998, **309**, 303; (b) M. Abde Akher and F. Smith, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 5859.
 38. A. Kumar and R. N. Mehrotra, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1975, **40**, 1248.
 39. K. K. Sengupta, B. A. Begum and B. B. Pal, *Carbohydr. Res.*, 1999, **315**, 70.

